

UPPRIORITY

UPPRIORITY REPORT

PRIORITISATION FOR UPDATING CLINICAL QUESTIONS WITHIN THE CLINICAL PRACTICE GUIDELINE ON THE TREATMENT OF CHRONIC HEART FAILURE

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1. SUMMARY

The clinical practice guideline (CPG) on the treatment of chronic heart failure was published in 2016 (date of last literature search May 2014). The CPG includes ten clinical questions and provides evidence-based recommendations on pharmacological, and non-pharmacological interventions for managing chronic heart failure.

Six appraisers assessed independently clinical questions, using the UpPriority tool, with the objective of prioritising clinical questions for updating.

The appraisers prioritised for updating one clinical question related to pharmacological treatment of chronic heart failure based on the ranking of priority scores. Eight clinical questions could be prioritised for updating and one clinical question was not prioritised for updating.

No relevant differences were observed in number of prioritized clinical questions between the different sections of the CG.

2. OBJECTIVE

To prioritise for updating the clinical questions included in the CPG on treatment of chronic heart failure [1].

3. METHODS

The UpPriority tool [2] was used to assess clinical questions from the CPG on the treatment of chronic heart failure [1]. We completed the following step-by-step process: 1) mapping of the clinical guideline, 2) developing of the priority survey, 3) assessing clinical questions according to the six priority items, 4) calculating and ranking the priority scores, 5) deciding on prioritised clinical questions for updating, and 6) developing the priority report.

Six appraisers independently assessed ten clinical questions using the UpPriority tool. The UpPriority tool consists of six items assessed using a 7-point Likert scale: 1) impact of outdated recommendations on safety, 2) availability of new relevant evidence, 3) context relevance of the clinical question, 4) methodological applicability of the clinical question, 5) user's interest, and 6) impact on access to health care. One appraiser only assessed the clinical questions related to pharmacological treatment (clinical questions 01 to 05) because it was his area of expertise.

The appraisers discussed the results and agreed to classify the clinical questions in three categories based on the ranking of priority scores: 1) clinical questions prioritised for updating, 2) clinical questions that could be prioritised for updating, and 3) clinical question not prioritised for updating.

4. LIST OF CLINICAL QUESTIONS

- **Clinical question 01** In patients older than 65 years with chronic heart failure and left ventricular ejection fraction less than 50%; is treatment with angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (or angiotensin II receptor blockers) recommended, along with beta-blockers and mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists, if there is no contraindication?
- **Clinical question 02** In patients with chronic heart failure and left ventricular ejection fraction more than 35%; is treatment with angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (or angiotensin II receptor blockers) recommended, along with beta-blockers and mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists, if there is no contraindication?
- **Clinical question 03** In the treatment of patients with chronic heart failure with NYHA class greater than or equal to II, left ventricular ejection fraction less than or equal to 35%, and receiving treatment with angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (or angiotensin II receptor blockers) along with beta-blockers; is eplerenone more effective than spironolactone?
- **Clinical question 04** In patients with chronic heart failure and ejection fraction less than or equal to 35%, receiving treatment with angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (or angiotensin II receptor blockers), along with beta-blockers and mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists, at maximum tolerated doses; is it recommended to substitute the angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (or angiotensin II receptor blockers) for sacubitril/valsartan?
- **Clinical question 05** In patients admitted for heart failure; is it recommended to schedule a priority follow-up visit (less than 30 days) after discharge from hospital?
- **Clinical question 06** In patients with chronic heart failure, are standardised hygienic-dietary measures recommended?
- **Clinical question 07** For the control of pharmacological treatment of patients with chronic heart failure; is monitoring of natriuretic peptides recommended in comparison with conventional control based on clinical conditions?
- **Clinical question 08** In patients with chronic heart failure and receiving treatment with angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (or angiotensin II receptor blockers), along with beta-blockers and mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists; is it recommended to be enrolled in a telemedicine program, if there is no contraindication?
- **Clinical question 09** In patients with chronic heart failure, what is the efficacy and safety of performing an exercise-based cardiac rehabilitation program versus not doing it to avoid hospitalisations, decrease mortality, and improve quality of life and functional capacity?
- **Clinical question 10** In patients older than 65 years with chronic heart failure and left ventricular ejection fraction less than 35%; is it recommended the use of an implantable cardioverter defibrillator to prevent sudden death?

5. RANKING OF PRIORITY SCORES

Table 1 and Figure 1 present the ranking of the clinical questions evaluated. Further information is available in the supplementary material.

6. PRIORITY DECISION

For this CPG, the clinical questions were classified in three categories based on the priority scores: 1) clinical questions prioritised for updating, 2) clinical questions that could be prioritised for updating, and 3) clinical question not prioritised for updating.

6.1. Clinical questions prioritised for updating

The appraisers prioritised for updating the following clinical question:

- **Clinical question 04** In patients with chronic heart failure and ejection fraction less than or equal to 35%, receiving treatment with angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (or angiotensin II receptor blockers), along with beta-blockers and mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists, at maximum tolerated doses; is it recommended to substitute the angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (or angiotensin II receptor blockers) for sacubitril/valsartan?

6.2. Clinical questions that could be prioritised for updating

The appraisers considered that the following clinical questions could be prioritised for updating (listed by priority score highest to lowest):

- **Clinical question 10** In patients older than 65 years with chronic heart failure and left ventricular ejection fraction less than 35%; is it recommended the use of an implantable cardioverter defibrillator to prevent sudden death?
- **Clinical question 08** In patients with chronic heart failure and receiving treatment with angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (or angiotensin II receptor blockers), along with beta-blockers and mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists; is it recommended to be enrolled in a telemedicine program, if there is no contraindication?
- **Clinical question 05** In patients admitted for heart failure; is it recommended to schedule early control (less than 30 days) after discharge from hospital?
- **Clinical question 09** In patients with chronic heart failure, what is the efficacy and safety of performing an exercise-based cardiac rehabilitation program versus not doing it to avoid hospitalisations, decrease mortality, and improve quality?
- **Clinical question 01** In patients older than 65 years with chronic heart failure and left ventricular ejection fraction less than 50%; is treatment with angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (or angiotensin II receptor blockers) recommended, along with beta-blockers and mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists, if there is no contraindication?
- **Clinical question 06** In patients with chronic heart failure, are standardised hygienic-dietary measures recommended?
- **Clinical question 07** For the control of pharmacological treatment of patients with chronic heart failure; is monitoring of natriuretic peptides recommended in comparison with conventional control based on clinical conditions?

- **Clinical question 02** In patients with chronic heart failure and left ventricular ejection fraction more than 35%; is treatment with angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (or angiotensin II receptor blockers) recommended, along with beta-blockers and mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists, if there is no contraindication?

6.3. Clinical question not prioritised for updating

The appraisers did not prioritise for updating the following clinical question:

- **Clinical question 03** In the treatment of patients with chronic heart failure with NYHA class greater than or equal to II, left ventricular ejection fraction less than or equal to 35%, and receiving treatment with angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (or angiotensin II receptor blockers) along with beta-blockers; is eplerenone more effective than spironolactone?

7. REASONS FOR PRIORITY DECISION

- None of the clinical questions assessed scored 5 or more in Item 01 (Impact of outdated recommendations on safety).
- One clinical question (04) have a priority score of 30 or more and scored 5 or more in item 02 (Availability of new relevant evidence). This clinical question was prioritised for updating.
- Eight clinical questions (10, 08, 05, 09, 01, 06, 07,02) have a priority score below 30 but scored 5 or more in Item 03 (Context relevance of the clinical question), Item 04 (Methodological applicability of the clinical question), and Item 05 (Users' interest). These clinical questions could be considered for updating following the ranking of priority scores ([Table 1](#)).
- One clinical question (03) score below 30 and scored lower than 5 in all of the priority items. In the case that this clinical question obtains a similar priority score in the next prioritisation process, it would be considered a candidate for the static list. Clinical questions in the static list are not checked as regularly as the other questions included in the CG [\[3\]](#).
- No relevant differences were observed in number of prioritized clinical questions between the different sections of the CG.

TABLE 1. RANKING OF PRIORITY SCORES

Clinical Question	Priority score ^a	Standard deviation ^b	Item score 01 ^{c,d}	Item score 02 ^{c,d}	Item score 03 ^{c,d}	Item score 04 ^{c,d}	Item score 05 ^{c,d}	Item score 06 ^{c,d}
CQ 04	31.50	2.51	3.33	5.00	6.17	5.83	6.00	5.17
CQ 10	29.67	3.93	4.17	3.83	5.50	5.50	5.17	5.50
CQ 08	29.50	3.39	3.00	4.17	6.00	5.50	5.83	5.00
CQ 05	29.17	3.54	3.17	4.00	6.00	5.33	5.83	4.83
CQ 09	29.17	3.60	3.17	4.17	5.67	5.50	5.67	5.00
CQ 01	29.00	3.03	2.83	3.50	6.50	5.33	6.17	4.67
CQ 06	28.67	2.80	3.17	4.00	5.67	5.83	6.00	4.00
CQ 07	28.50	4.42	3.00	4.33	6.00	5.83	5.17	4.17
CQ 02	28.33	4.59	2.83	3.50	6.00	5.33	6.00	4.67
CQ 03	22.50	7.69	3.17	2.00	4.83	4.67	4.17	3.67

Abbreviation: CQ: Clinical question. ^a Priority scores ordered from higher to lower. ^b Standard deviation ordered from lower to higher. ^c Priority items: Item 01 Impact of out-dated recommendations on safety; Item 02 Availability of new relevant evidence; Item 03 Context relevance of the clinical question; Item 04 Methodological applicability of the clinical question; Item 05 Users' interest; and Item 06 Impact on access to health care. ^d Items with a score of 5 or more are highlighted in red.

FIGURE 1. RANKING OF PRIORITY SCORES

8. REFERENCES

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UPPRIORITY

UPPRIORITY REPORT

PRIORITISATION FOR UPDATING CLINICAL QUESTIONS WITHIN THE CLINICAL PRACTICE GUIDELINE ON INHERITED RETINAL DYSTROPHIES

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1. SUMMARY

The clinical practice guideline (CPG) on inherited retinal dystrophies was published in 2017 (date of last literature search June 2016). The CPG includes 29 clinical questions and 10 subquestions providing evidence-based recommendations on diagnosis, management, rehabilitation, information and communication needs for people with IRD and careers.

Six appraisers independently assessed the clinical questions using the UpPriority tool with the objective of prioritising clinical questions for updating.

The appraisers prioritised for updating eight clinical questions related to management of inherited retinal dystrophies and associated complications. The other clinical questions were not prioritised for updating.

2. OBJECTIVE

To prioritise for updating the clinical questions included in the CPG on inherited retinal dystrophies [1].

3. METHODS

The UpPriority tool [2] was used to assess clinical questions from the CPG on inherited retinal dystrophies [1]. We completed the following step-by-step process: 1) mapping of the clinical guideline, 2) developing of the priority survey, 3) assessing clinical questions according to the six priority items, 4) calculating and ranking the priority scores, 5) deciding on prioritised clinical questions for updating, and 6) developing the priority report.

Six appraisers independently assessed ten clinical questions using the UpPriority tool. The UpPriority tool consists of six items assessed using a 7-point Likert scale: 1) impact of outdated recommendations on safety, 2) availability of new relevant evidence, 3) context relevance of the clinical question, 4) methodological applicability of the clinical question, 5) user's interest, and 6) impact on access to health care. One appraiser only assessed the clinical questions related to pharmacological treatment (clinical questions 01 to 05) because it was his area of expertise.

The appraisers discussed the results and agreed to classify the clinical questions in two categories based on the ranking of priority scores: 1) clinical questions prioritised for updating and 2) clinical question not prioritised for updating.

4. LIST OF CLINICAL QUESTIONS

- **Clinical question 01** What are the Inherited Retinal Dystrophies (IRD)?
- **Clinical question 02** In paediatric patients attending primary care (or emergency services), Which are the signs and symptoms of IRD?
- **Clinical question 03** In adult patients attending primary care (or emergency services), Which are the signs and symptoms of IRD?
- **Clinical question 04** In adult patients suspected of having IRD, which investigations should be performed to confirm the diagnosis? In which order? Who should be assessed?
- **Clinical question 05** How is an electrophysiology test conducted? What are its indications? Which tests have to be requested?
- **Clinical question 06.01** What are the most frequent diagnostic criteria of IRD?
- **Clinical question 06.02** What are the most frequent diagnostic criteria of IRD? - Retinitis pigmentosa, Usher syndrome, Bardet-Biedl syndrome
- **Clinical question 06.03** What are the most frequent diagnostic criteria of IRD? - Progressive cone dystrophy (PCD) and rod and cone dystrophy (CORD)
- **Clinical question 06.04** What are the most frequent diagnostic criteria of IRD? - Stargardt disease and fundus flavimaculatus
- **Clinical question 06.05** What are the most frequent diagnostic criteria of IRD? - Stationary congenital night blindness
- **Clinical question 06.06** What are the most frequent diagnostic criteria of IRD? - Best macular vitelliform dystrophy or Best disease
- **Clinical question 06.07** What are the most frequent diagnostic criteria of IRD? - X-linked juvenile retinoschisis (XLRS)
- **Clinical question 06.08** What are the most frequent diagnostic criteria of IRD? - Choroideremia
- **Clinical question 06.09** What are the most frequent diagnostic criteria of IRD? - Girata atrophy
- **Clinical question 06.10** What are the most frequent diagnostic criteria of IRD? - Leber congenital amaurosis
- **Clinical question 07** What are the signs and symptoms of a syndromic IRD?
- **Clinical question 08** When is a genetic diagnosis indicated in patients with IRD? How should it be performed?
- **Clinical question 09** When is genetic counselling indicated in people with IRD? How should it be performed?
- **Clinical question 10** What is the role of the GP in the care of people with IRD?
- **Clinical question 11** How often should the ophthalmologist assess people with IRD?
- **Clinical question 12** What are the referral criteria for specialist otolaryngology assessment for people with IRD?
- **Clinical question 13** What is the efficacy and safety of the pharmacological treatments available for IRD?
- **Clinical question 14** What is the efficacy of neuroprotection for the treatment of IRD?
- **Clinical question 15** What is the efficacy and safety of electronic retinal implants for the treatment of IRD?
- **Clinical question 16** What is the efficacy and safety of retinal transplants for treatment of IRD?
- **Clinical question 17** What is the efficacy and safety of gene therapy for the treatment of IRD?
- **Clinical question 18.01** What is the efficacy and safety of dietary supplements in people with IRD? - Vitamins
- **Clinical question 18.02** What is the efficacy and safety of dietary supplements in people with IRD? – Other supplements.
- **Clinical question 19** What are the benefits of low vision rehabilitation in people with IRD? In which cases would be it useful?

- **Clinical question 20** Is counselling and/or psychological treatment effective in people with IRD?
- **Clinical question 21** Structured education for family members and patients with IRD: When, how, by who and which components should be included?
- **Clinical question 22** What lifestyle measures should be advised in people with IRD?
- **Clinical question 23** When should an associated cataract be treated surgically? Are there any specific manoeuvres that should be recommended?
- **Clinical question 24** How can a retinal detachment in vitreoretinal dystrophies be prevented?
- **Clinical question 25** How should a retinal detachment be treated in people with IRD?
- **Clinical question 26** How should macular oedema associated with IRD be treated?
- **Clinical question 27** How should neovascular membranes associated with IRD be treated? In paediatric patients, is there any particular issue that should be considered?
- **Clinical question 28** Is there any risk during pregnancy and breastfeeding in women with IRD?
- **Clinical question 29** What are the information and communication needs about their health condition and provision of care in people with HDR and their caregivers?

5. RANKING OF PRIORITY SCORES

Table 1 and Figure 1 present the ranking of the clinical questions evaluated. Further information is available in the supplementary material.

6. PRIORITY DECISION

For this CPG, the clinical questions were classified in two categories based on the priority scores: 1) clinical questions prioritised for updating and 2) clinical question not prioritised for updating.

6.1. Clinical questions prioritised for updating

The appraisers prioritised for updating the following clinical question:

- **Clinical question 17** What is the efficacy and safety of gene therapy for the treatment of IRD?
- **Clinical question 13** What is the efficacy and safety of the pharmacological treatments available for IRD?
- **Clinical question 18.01** What is the efficacy and safety of dietary supplements in people with IRD? – Vitamins
- **Clinical question 15** What is the efficacy and safety of electronic retinal implants for the treatment of IRD?
- **Clinical question 24** How can a retinal detachment in vitreoretinal dystrophies be prevented?
- **Clinical question 16** What is the efficacy and safety of retinal transplants for treatment of IRD?
- **Clinical question 26** How should macular oedema associated with IRD be treated?
- **Clinical question 25** How should a retinal detachment be treated in people with IRD?

6.2. Clinical question not prioritised for updating

The appraisers did not prioritise for updating the following clinical question (listed by priority score highest to lowest):

- **Clinical question 08** When is a genetic diagnosis indicated in patients with IRD? How should it be performed?
- **Clinical question 11** How often should the ophthalmologist assess people with IRD?
- **Clinical question 18.02** What is the efficacy and safety of dietary supplements in people with IRD? – Other supplements.

- **Clinical question 19** What are the benefits of low vision rehabilitation in people with IRD? In which cases would be it useful?
- **Clinical question 12** What are the referral criteria for specialist otolaryngology assessment for people with IRD?
- **Clinical question 10** What is the role of the GP in the care of people with IRD?
- **Clinical question 06.10** What are the most frequent diagnostic criteria of IRD? - Leber congenital amaurosis
- **Clinical question 20** Is counselling and/or psychological treatment effective in people with IRD
- **Clinical question 21** Structured education for family members and patients with IRD: When, how, by who and which components should be included?
- **Clinical question 09** When is genetic counselling indicated in people with IRD? How should it be performed?
- **Clinical question 22** What lifestyle measures should be advised in people with IRD?
- **Clinical question 06.01** What are the most frequent diagnostic criteria of IRD?
- **Clinical question 23** When should an associated cataract be treated surgically? Are there any specific manoeuvres that should be recommended?
- **Clinical question 04** In adult patients suspected of having IRD, which investigations should be performed to confirm the diagnosis? In which order? Who should be assessed?
- **Clinical question 06.09** What are the most frequent diagnostic criteria of IRD? - Girata atrophy
- **Clinical question 06.02** What are the most frequent diagnostic criteria of IRD? - Retinitis pigmentosa, Usher syndrome, Bardet-Biedl syndrome
- **Clinical question 06.03** What are the most frequent diagnostic criteria of IRD? - Progressive cone dystrophy (PCD) and rod and cone dystrophy (CORD)
- **Clinical question 27** How should neovascular membranes associated with IRD be treated? In paediatric patients, is there any particular issue that should be considered?
- **Clinical question 06.04** What are the most frequent diagnostic criteria of IRD? - Stargardt disease and fundus flavimaculatus
- **Clinical question 06.08** What are the most frequent diagnostic criteria of IRD? - Choroideremia
- **Clinical question 14** What is the efficacy of neuroprotection for the treatment of IRD?
- **Clinical question 06.06** What are the most frequent diagnostic criteria of IRD? - Best macular vitelliform dystrophy or Best disease
- **Clinical question 07** What are the signs and symptoms of a syndromic inherited retinal dystrophy?
- **Clinical question 28** Is there any risk during pregnancy and breastfeeding in women with IRD?
- **Clinical question 29** What are the information and communication needs about their health condition and provision of care in people with HDR and their caregivers?
- **Clinical question 06.05** What are the most frequent diagnostic criteria of IRD? - Stationary congenital night blindness
- **Clinical question 05** How is an electrophysiology test conducted? What are its indications? Which tests have to be requested?
- **Clinical question 03** In adult patients attending primary care (or emergency services), Which are the signs and symptoms of IRD?
- **Clinical question 02** In paediatric patients attending primary care (or emergency services), Which are the signs and symptoms of IRD?
- **Clinical question 01** What are the inherited retinal dystrophies (IRD)?

7. REASONS FOR PRIORITY DECISION

- None of the clinical questions assessed scored 30 or more.
- Eight clinical questions (17, 13, 18.01, 15, 24, 16, 26, and 25) scored 5 or more in Item 01 (Impact of outdated recommendations on safety). Given the implications on safety, these clinical questions were prioritised for updating.
- The other clinical questions have a priority score below 30. These clinical questions should not be prioritised for updating.
- Most of the clinical questions prioritised for updating are from the CG sections of management of IRD and management of associated complications. The prioritisation for updating could focus on these two sections of the CG.

TABLE 1. RANKING OF PRIORITY SCORES

Clinical Question	Priority score ^a	Standard deviation ^b	Item score 01 ^{c,d}	Item score 02 ^{c,d}	Item score 03 ^{c,d}	Item score 04 ^{c,d}	Item score 05 ^{c,d}	Item score 06 ^{c,d}
CQ17	15.38	5.99	5.33	5.17	6.17	5.17	6.17	5.33
CQ13	15.23	6.39	5.33	4.33	6.17	6.00	6.33	4.83
CQ08	14.77	8.07	4.83	3.00	6.17	6.17	6.50	5.33
CQ18.01	14.69	5.81	5.67	3.17	6.17	6.17	6.33	4.33
CQ11	14.00	5.28	4.50	3.33	6.17	6.00	6.00	4.33
CQ15	14.00	8.66	5.50	4.17	5.50	5.67	5.67	3.83
CQ18.02	13.77	6.49	4.83	2.83	5.67	5.83	6.17	4.50
CQ19	13.77	6.74	4.17	3.00	6.00	5.67	6.00	5.00
CQ12	13.62	5.09	4.33	3.33	6.00	5.83	6.00	4.00
CQ10	13.62	5.32	4.50	2.83	6.00	6.00	5.67	4.50
CQ06.10	13.62	8.17	3.33	4.33	5.83	5.50	6.17	4.33
CQ20	13.54	6.56	3.67	2.83	5.33	5.17	6.00	3.50
CQ21	13.46	6.49	3.67	2.50	4.67	4.83	4.50	3.17
CQ09	13.38	9.42	4.17	2.67	5.83	5.83	6.17	4.33
CQ22	13.15	6.44	4.33	3.33	5.17	5.50	6.00	3.17
CQ06.01	13.08	8.80	3.83	3.00	5.67	5.67	5.83	4.33
CQ23	12.92	6.78	4.50	3.00	6.00	5.67	6.00	4.67
CQ24	12.92	6.78	5.00	4.17	6.00	5.67	6.00	4.50
CQ04	12.85	11.55	4.17	2.83	5.67	5.50	5.67	4.00
CQ16	12.38	9.37	5.33	3.17	4.67	5.17	5.33	3.17
CQ06.09	12.31	11.02	4.17	2.33	5.67	5.67	5.67	3.17
CQ26	12.23	6.80	5.50	3.50	6.00	6.00	6.17	4.33
CQ25	12.23	6.98	5.00	3.33	6.00	6.00	6.00	4.67
CQ06.02	12.23	10.33	4.00	2.83	5.50	5.50	5.83	2.83
CQ06.03	12.15	10.33	3.50	3.00	5.67	5.50	5.83	2.83
CQ27	12.08	6.43	4.83	3.17	6.00	6.00	5.83	4.50
CQ06.04	12.08	9.95	3.33	3.00	5.50	5.33	6.17	2.83
CQ06.08	12.08	10.30	3.67	2.33	5.50	5.50	6.00	3.17
CQ14	12.00	7.54	3.83	3.17	5.17	5.17	5.00	3.67
CQ06.06	12.00	10.77	3.67	2.67	5.83	5.33	5.67	2.83
CQ07	11.85	10.84	3.83	2.67	5.50	5.50	5.17	3.00
CQ06.07	11.85	10.98	3.67	2.17	5.67	5.33	5.83	3.00
CQ28	11.77	6.69	4.50	3.33	5.83	5.83	6.00	4.00
CQ29	11.62	6.55	4.00	2.50	6.00	6.00	6.17	3.83
CQ06.05	11.46	10.38	3.33	2.50	5.67	5.00	5.50	2.83
CQ05	11.38	8.19	3.50	2.67	5.00	4.67	4.67	4.17
CQ03	11.31	11.10	3.67	2.33	5.17	4.67	5.50	3.17
CQ02	11.15	11.20	3.33	2.00	5.33	4.83	5.50	3.17
CQ01	8.69	9.22	1.67	1.67	4.50	4.50	4.67	1.83

Abbreviation: CQ: Clinical question. ^a Priority scores ordered from higher to lower. ^b Standard deviation ordered from lower to higher. ^c Priority items: Item 01 Impact of out-dated recommendations on safety; Item 02 Availability of new relevant evidence; Item 03 Context relevance of the clinical question; Item 04 Methodological applicability of the clinical question; Item 05 Users' interest; and Item 06 Impact on access to health care. ^d Items with a score of 5 or more are highlighted in red.

FIGURE 1. RANKING OF PRIORITY SCORES

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UPPRIORITY

UPPRIORITY REPORT

PRIORITISATION FOR UPDATING CLINICAL QUESTIONS WITHIN THE CLINICAL PRACTICE GUIDELINE ON THE MANAGEMENT OF VASOMOTOR AND VAGINAL SYMPTOMS ASSOCIATED WITH MENOPAUSE AND POSTMENOPAUSE

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1. SUMMARY

The clinical practice guideline (CPG) on the management of vasomotor and vaginal symptoms associated with menopause and postmenopause was published in 2017 (date of last literature search March 2014). The CPG includes 20 clinical questions and provides evidence-based recommendations on: 1) definitions, 2) treatment of vasomotor symptoms, and 3) treatment of vaginal symptoms.

Five appraisers assessed independently clinical questions, using the UpPriority tool, with the objective of prioritising clinical questions for updating.

The appraisers prioritised for updating four clinical questions related to treatment of vasomotor symptoms based on the ranking of priority scores.

2. OBJECTIVE

To prioritise for updating the clinical questions included in the CPG on the management of vasomotor and vaginal symptoms associated with menopause and postmenopause [[Error! Reference source not found.](#)].

3. METHODS

The UpPriority tool [[2](#)] was used to assess clinical questions from the CPG on the management of vasomotor and vaginal symptoms associated with menopause and postmenopause [[Error! Reference source not found.](#)]. We completed the following step-by-step process: 1) mapping of the clinical guideline, 2) developing of the priority survey, 3) assessing clinical questions according to the six priority items, 4) calculating and ranking the priority scores, 5) deciding on prioritised clinical questions for updating, and 6) developing the priority report.

Five appraisers independently assessed ten clinical questions using the UpPriority tool. The UpPriority tool consists of six items assessed using a 7-point Likert scale: 1) impact of outdated recommendations on safety, 2) availability of new relevant evidence, 3) context relevance of the clinical question, 4) methodological applicability of the clinical question, 5) user's interest, and 6) impact on access to health care.

The appraisers discussed the results and agreed to classify the clinical questions in three categories based on the ranking of priority scores: 1) clinical questions prioritised for updating, 2) clinical questions that could be prioritised for updating, and 3) clinical question not prioritised for updating.

4. LIST OF CLINICAL QUESTIONS

- **Clinical question 01** What symptoms have a causal association with a decrease in the oestrogen levels in women during menopause?
- **Clinical question 02** What is the most recommended method to assess vasomotor symptoms? Is there any diagnostic scale?
- **Clinical question 03** What can cause hot flashes other than menopause?
- **Clinical question 04** In women with vasomotor symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of lifestyles modifications?
- **Clinical question 05** In women with vasomotor symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of the hormone therapy with oestrogens, and oestrogens combined with gestagens?
- **Clinical question 06** In women with vasomotor symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of the hormonal therapy with gestagens?
- **Clinical question 07** In women with vasomotor symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of the hormonal therapy with androgens?
- **Clinical question 08** In women with vasomotor symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of the hormonal therapy with tibolone?
- **Clinical question 09** In women with vasomotor symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of antidepressants medications?
- **Clinical question 10** In women with vasomotor symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of other pharmacological treatments like gabapentin, methyldopa, and clonidine?
- **Clinical question 11** In women with vasomotor symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of the phytotherapy?
- **Clinical question 12** In women with vasomotor symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of the non-pharmacological treatments?
- **Clinical question 13** In women with vasomotor symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of other alternative therapies?
- **Clinical question 14** In women with vaginal symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of lifestyles modificationa?
- **Clinical question 15** In women with vaginal symptoms during peri and postmenopause, Wwhat is the efficacy and safety of the oestrogens?
- **Clinical question 16** In women with vaginal symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of the gestagens?
- **Clinical question 17** In women with vaginal symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of the hormonal therapy with tibolone?
- **Clinical question 18** In women with vaginal symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of the phytotherapy?
- **Clinical question 19** In women with vaginal symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of the selective oestrogen receptor modulators (SERMs)?
- **Clinical question 20** In women with vaginal symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of the vaginal lubricants and moisturizers?

5. RANKING OF PRIORITY SCORES

Table 1 and Figure 1 present the ranking of the clinical questions evaluated. Further information is available in the supplementary material.

6. PRIORITY DECISION

For this CPG, the clinical questions were classified in three categories based on the priority scores: 1) clinical questions prioritised for updating, 2) clinical questions that could be prioritised for updating, and 3) clinical question not prioritised for updating.

6.1. Clinical questions prioritised for updating

The appraisers prioritised for updating the following clinical questions:

- **Clinical question 05** In women with vasomotor symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of the hormone therapy with oestrogens, and oestrogens combined with gestagens?
- **Clinical question 08** In women with vasomotor symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of the hormonal therapy with tibolone?
- **Clinical question 09** In women with vasomotor symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of antidepressants medications?
- **Clinical question 10** In women with vasomotor symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of other pharmacological treatments like gabapentin, methyldopa, and clonidine?

6.2. Clinical questions that could be prioritised for updating

The appraisers considered that the following clinical questions could be prioritised for updating (listed by priority score highest to lowest):

- **Clinical question 15** In women with vaginal symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of the oestrogens?
- **Clinical question 06** In women with vasomotor symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of the hormonal therapy with gestagens?
- **Clinical question 07** In women with vasomotor symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of the hormonal therapy with androgens?
- **Clinical question 19** In women with vaginal symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of the selective oestrogen receptor modulators (SERMs)?
- **Clinical question 14** In women with vaginal symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of lifestyles modificationa?
- **Clinical question 04** In women with vasomotor symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of lifestyles modifications?
- **Clinical question 03** What can cause hot flashes other than menopause?
- **Clinical question 20** In women with vaginal symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of the vaginal lubricants and moisturizers?
- **Clinical question 17** In women with vaginal symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of the hormonal therapy with tibolone?
- **Clinical question 02** What is the most recommended method to assess vasomotor symptoms? Is there any diagnostic scale?

- **Clinical question 01** What symptoms have a causal association with a decrease in the oestrogen levels in women during menopause?
- **Clinical question 16** In women with vaginal symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of the gestagens?
- **Clinical question 18** In women with vaginal symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of the phytotherapy?

6.3. Clinical question not prioritised for updating

The appraisers did not prioritise for updating the following clinical questions:

- **Clinical question 11** In women with vasomotor symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of the phytotherapy?
- **Clinical question 12** In women with vasomotor symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of the non-pharmacological treatments?
- **Clinical question 13** In women with vasomotor symptoms during peri and postmenopause, what is the efficacy and safety of other alternative therapies?

7. REASONS FOR PRIORITY DECISION

- Four clinical questions 05, 08, 09 and 10 scored 5 or more in Item 01 (Impact of out-dated recommendations on safety). Given the implications on safety, these clinical questions were prioritised for updating.
- Three clinical questions (15, 06, and 07) have a priority score of 30 or more but a score below 5 in item 02 (Availability of new relevant evidence). These clinical questions could be considered for updating.
- Ten clinical questions have a priority score below 30 but with a standard deviation that could pass this priority score (19, 14, 04, 03, 20, 17, 02, 01, 16, and 18). These clinical questions could be considered for updating considering following the ranking of the priority scores ([Table 1](#)).
- Three clinical questions (11, 12 and 13) have a priority score below 30 and scored lower than 5 in most of the other priority items (item 03- Context relevance of the clinical question, item 04 - Methodological applicability of the clinical question, item 05 - Users' interest and item 06 - Impact on access to health care). These clinical questions should not be prioritised for updating. In the case that these clinical questions obtain a similar priority score in the next prioritisation process, it would be considered candidates for the static list. Clinical questions in the static list are not checked as regularly as the other questions included in the CG [\[3\]](#).
- Most of the clinical questions prioritised for updating are from the CG section 'treatment of vasomotor symptoms'. The prioritisation for updating could focus on this section of the CG.

TABLE 1. RANKING OF PRIORITY SCORES

Clinical Question	Priority score ^a	Standard deviation ^b	Item score 01 ^{c,d}	Item score 02 ^{c,d}	Item score 03 ^{c,d}	Item score 04 ^{c,d}	Item score 05 ^{c,d}	Item score 06 ^{c,d}
CQ05	37.00	3.61	5.60	5.20	6.80	6.80	6.80	5.80
CQ15	31.20	4.97	4.20	4.20	6.00	5.80	6.40	4.60
CQ08	31.00	8.54	5.40	4.00	5.80	5.40	5.60	4.80
CQ06	30.20	9.96	4.20	4.60	5.40	5.40	5.80	4.80
CQ07	30.20	11.50	4.60	4.40	5.60	5.40	5.60	4.60
CQ09	29.60	7.89	5.20	4.00	5.20	5.40	5.60	4.20
CQ19	28.40	3.13	2.20	6.00	6.00	5.40	4.40	4.40
CQ14	27.80	4.44	3.60	3.80	5.60	5.60	5.80	3.40
CQ04	27.40	12.74	4.40	3.20	4.80	5.80	5.00	4.20
CQ03	27.20	7.05	3.20	3.20	6.00	5.60	6.20	3.00
CQ20	26.80	4.60	3.60	3.80	5.40	5.40	5.40	3.20
CQ17	26.60	11.84	4.00	3.80	5.20	4.80	4.80	4.00
CQ02	26.20	4.97	1.60	4.80	6.00	5.00	5.60	3.20
CQ01	24.80	6.80	2.80	3.60	4.80	5.80	5.00	2.80
CQ16	24.80	11.39	3.40	4.00	5.00	4.80	4.40	3.20
CQ18	24.40	8.50	2.00	4.00	5.00	4.40	4.80	4.20
CQ11	23.80	1.64	2.80	3.40	4.80	4.20	5.40	3.20
CQ12	23.80	4.32	2.00	3.80	4.80	4.40	5.20	3.60
CQ10	23.60	5.77	5.40	3.00	3.80	3.80	3.60	4.00
CQ13	23.00	5.61	2.40	3.60	4.60	4.20	4.60	3.60

Abbreviation: CQ: Clinical question. ^a Priority scores ordered from higher to lower. ^b Standard deviation ordered from lower to higher. ^c Priority items: Item 01 Impact of out-dated recommendations on safety; Item 02 Availability of new relevant evidence; Item 03 Context relevance of the clinical question; Item 04 Methodological applicability of the clinical question; Item 05 Users' interest; and Item 06 Impact on access to health care. ^d Items with a score of 5 or more are highlighted in red.

FIGURE 1. RANKING OF PRIORITY SCORES

8. REFERENCES

1. Grupo de trabajo de la Guía de Práctica Clínica sobre el abordaje de síntomas vasomotores y vaginales asociados a la menopausia y la postmenopausia. Guía de Práctica Clínica sobre el abordaje de síntomas vasomotores y vaginales asociados a la menopausia y la postmenopausia. Ministerio de Sanidad, Servicios Sociales e Igualdad. Agencia de Evaluación de Tecnologías Sanitarias de Andalucía (AETSA); 2017. Guías de Práctica Clínica en el SNS. Available at: <https://portal.guiasalud.es/gpc/menopausia-postmenopausia/> [Accessed September 11, 2020].
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UPPRIORITY

UPPRIORITY REPORT

PRIORITISATION FOR UPDATING CLINICAL QUESTIONS WITHIN THE CLINICAL PRACTICE GUIDELINE ON OPEN ANGLE GLAUCOMA

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1. SUMMARY

The clinical practice guideline (CPG) on open angle glaucoma was published in 2017 (date of last literature search September 2013). The CPG includes 38 clinical questions and provides evidence-based recommendations on: 1) risk factors, screening and diagnosis, 2) pharmacological treatment, 3) laser treatment, 4) surgical treatment, 5) locoregional anaesthesia for glaucoma surgery, and 6) follow-up.

Thirteen appraisers assessed independently clinical questions, using the UpPriority tool, with the objective of prioritising clinical questions for updating.

No relevant differences were observed in number of prioritized clinical questions between the different sections of the CG.

2. OBJECTIVE

To prioritise for updating the clinical questions included in the CPG on open angle glaucoma [Error! Reference source not found.].

3. METHODS

The UpPriority tool [2] was used to assess clinical questions from the CPG on the treatment of chronic heart failure [Error! Reference source not found.]. We completed the following step-by-step process: 1) mapping of the clinical guideline, 2) developing of the priority survey, 3) assessing clinical questions according to the six priority items, 4) calculating and ranking the priority scores, 5) deciding on prioritised clinical questions for updating, and 6) developing the priority report.

Thirteen appraisers independently assessed ten clinical questions using the UpPriority tool. The UpPriority tool consists of six items assessed using a 7-point Likert scale: 1) impact of outdated recommendations on safety, 2) availability of new relevant evidence, 3) context relevance of the clinical question, 4) methodological applicability of the clinical question, 5) user's interest, and 6) impact on access to health care.

The appraisers discussed the results and agreed to classify the clinical questions in three categories based on the ranking of priority scores: 1) clinical questions prioritised for updating, 2) clinical questions that could be prioritised for updating, and 3) clinical question not prioritised for updating.

4. LIST OF CLINICAL QUESTIONS

- **Clinical question 01** In adult patients, what are the risk factors of developing open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 02** In people with glaucoma risk factors, what screening test(s) should be conducted and how often for an early open-angle glaucoma diagnosis?
- **Clinical question 03** In people with suspected glaucoma, what minimal tests should be conducted to diagnose and classify the type of glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 04** In adult patients, what is the recommended pharmacological treatment for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 05** In adult patients, which of these drugs (parasympathomimetics versus beta-blockers) are recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 06** In adult patients, which of these drugs (carbonic anhydrase inhibitors versus beta-blockers) are recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 07** In adult patients, which of the following drugs (prostaglandin analogues versus beta-blockers) are recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 08** In adult patients, which of the following drugs (prostaglandin analogues versus carbonic anhydrase inhibitors) are recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 09** In adult patients, which of the following drugs (beta-blockers versus selective alpha2 agonists) is recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 10** In adult patients, which of the following prostaglandin analogues are recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 11** In adult patients, which of the following drugs (prostaglandin analogues versus selective alpha2 agonists) are recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 12** In adult patients, which of the following beta-blockers are recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 13** In adult patients, is the use of fixed drug combinations versus non-fixed combinations of these drugs recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 14** In adult patients, is the use of preservative-free drugs versus preservative drugs recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 15** In adult patients, is laser trabeculoplasty recommended for open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 16** In adult patients, is diode-laser trabeculoplasty versus argon-laser trabeculoplasty recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 17** In adult patients, is selective laser trabeculoplasty versus argon laser trabeculoplasty recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 18** In adult patients, is laser trabeculoplasty versus pharmacological treatment recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 19** In adult patients, is laser trabeculoplasty associated with pharmacological treatment versus pharmacological treatment recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 20** In adult patients, is laser trabeculoplasty versus trabeculectomy recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 21** In adult patients, what is the recommended surgical treatment for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 22** In adult patients, is trabeculectomy versus pharmacological treatment recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?

- **Clinical question 23** In adult patients, is antimetabolite-associated trabeculectomy versus trabeculectomy alone recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 24** In adult patients, is non-penetrating surgery versus trabeculectomy recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 25** In adult patients, is non-penetrating antimetabolite-associated surgery versus non-penetrating surgery alone recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 26** In adult patients, is the use of use of viscocanalostomy versus deep sclerectomy recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 27** In adult patients, is non-penetrating non-implant surgery versus non-penetrating implant surgery recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 28** In adult patients, is the use of an Ex-Press implant versus trabeculectomy recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 29** In adult patients, are drainage devices (valved or not) versus trabeculectomy recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 30** In adult patients, is micro trabeculectomy versus trabeculectomy recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 31** In adult patients, are microinvasive techniques (MICS) versus trabeculectomy recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 32** In adult patients, what is the recommended locoregional anaesthesia technique in open-angle glaucoma surgery?
- **Clinical question 33** In adult patients, is topical anaesthesia versus retrobulbar anaesthesia recommended in open-angle glaucoma surgery?
- **Clinical question 34** In adult patients, is topical anaesthesia versus subtenonian anaesthesia recommended in open-angle glaucoma surgery?
- **Clinical question 35** In adult patients, is topical anaesthesia versus peribulbar anaesthesia recommended in open-angle glaucoma surgery?
- **Clinical question 36** In adult patients, is contact anaesthesia versus other anaesthetic techniques recommended in open-angle glaucoma surgery?
- **Clinical question 37** In adult patients, is subtenonian anaesthesia versus retrobulbar anaesthesia recommended in open-angle glaucoma surgery?
- **Clinical question 38** In the progress monitoring of adults with open-angle glaucoma, which follow-up examinations should be conducted and how often?

5. RANKING OF PRIORITY SCORES

Table 1 and Figure 1 present the ranking of the clinical questions evaluated. Further information is available in the supplementary material attached.

6. PRIORITY DECISION

For this CPG, the clinical questions were classified in three categories based on the priority scores: 1) clinical questions prioritised for updating, 2) clinical questions that could be prioritised for updating, and 3) clinical question not prioritised for updating.

6.1. Clinical questions prioritised for updating

The appraisers prioritised for updating the following clinical questions:

- **Clinical question 18** In adult patients, is laser trabeculectomy versus pharmacological treatment recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 31** In adult patients, are microinvasive techniques (MICS) versus trabeculectomy recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 01** In adult patients, what are the risk factors of developing open-angle glaucoma?

6.2. Clinical questions that could be prioritised for updating

The appraisers considered that the following clinical questions could be prioritised for updating (listed by priority score highest to lowest):

- **Clinical question 38** In the progress monitoring of adults with open-angle glaucoma, which follow-up examinations should be conducted and how often?
- **Clinical question 22** In adult patients, is trabeculectomy versus pharmacological treatment recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 14** In adult patients, is the use of preservative-free drugs versus preservative drugs recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 21** In adult patients, what is the recommended surgical treatment for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 15** In adult patients, is laser trabeculectomy recommended for open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 03** In people with suspected glaucoma, what minimal tests should be conducted to diagnose and classify the type of glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 23** In adult patients, is antimetabolite-associated trabeculectomy versus trabeculectomy alone recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 02** In people with glaucoma risk factors, what screening test(s) should be conducted and how often for an early open-angle glaucoma diagnosis?
- **Clinical question 17** In adult patients, is selective laser trabeculectomy versus argon laser trabeculectomy recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 29** In adult patients, are drainage devices (valved or not) versus trabeculectomy recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 25** In adult patients, is non-penetrating antimetabolite-associated surgery versus non-penetrating surgery alone recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?

- **Clinical question 24** In adult patients, is non-penetrating surgery versus trabeculectomy recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 28** In adult patients, is the use of an Ex-Press implant versus trabeculectomy recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 04** In adult patients, what is the recommended pharmacological treatment for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 27** In adult patients, is non-penetrating non-implant surgery versus non-penetrating implant surgery recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 20** In adult patients, is laser trabeculectomy versus trabeculectomy recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 19** In adult patients, is laser trabeculectomy associated with pharmacological treatment versus pharmacological treatment recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 26** In adult patients, is the use of use of viscocanalostomy versus deep sclerectomy recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 10** In adult patients, which of the following prostaglandin analogues are recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 07** In adult patients, which of the following drugs (prostaglandin analogues versus beta-blockers) are recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 13** In adult patients, is the use of fixed drug combinations versus non-fixed combinations of these drugs recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 09** In adult patients, which of the following drugs (beta-blockers versus selective alpha2 agonists) is recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 32** In adult patients, what is the recommended locoregional anaesthesia technique in open-angle glaucoma surgery?
- **Clinical question 06** In adult patients, which of these drugs (carbonic anhydrase inhibitors versus beta-blockers) are recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 36** In adult patients, is contact anaesthesia versus other anaesthetic techniques recommended in open-angle glaucoma surgery?
- **Clinical question 34** In adult patients, is topical anaesthesia versus subtenonian anaesthesia recommended in open-angle glaucoma surgery?

6.3. Clinical question not prioritised for updating

The appraisers did not prioritise for updating the following clinical questions:

- **Clinical question 11** In adult patients, which of the following drugs (prostaglandin analogues versus selective alpha2 agonists) are recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 12** In adult patients, which of the following beta-blockers are recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 33** In adult patients, is topical anaesthesia versus retrobulbar anaesthesia recommended in open-angle glaucoma surgery?
- **Clinical question 08** In adult patients, which of the following drugs (prostaglandin analogues versus carbonic anhydrase inhibitors) are recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 37** In adult patients, is subtenonian anaesthesia versus retrobulbar anaesthesia recommended in open-angle glaucoma surgery?

- **Clinical question 16** In adult patients, is diode-laser trabeculectomy versus argon-laser trabeculectomy recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 05** In adult patients, which of these drugs (parasympathomimetics versus beta-blockers) are recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?
- **Clinical question 35** In adult patients, is topical anaesthesia versus peribulbar anaesthesia recommended in open-angle glaucoma surgery?
- **Clinical question 30** In adult patients, is micro trabeculectomy versus trabeculectomy recommended for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma?

7. REASONS FOR PRIORITY DECISION

- None of the clinical questions assessed scored 5 or more in Item 01 (Impact of out-dated recommendations on safety).
- Two clinical questions (18 and 31) have a priority score of 30 or more and scored 5 or more in item 02 (Availability of new relevant evidence). These clinical questions were prioritised for updating.
- Twenty-five clinical questions have a priority score: 1) 30 or more but scored lower than 5 in item 02 (38, 22, 14, 21, and 15) or 2) below 30 but with a standard deviation that could pass this priority score (03, 23, 02, 17, 29, 25, 24, 01, 28, 04, 27, 20, 19, 26, 10, 07, 13, 09, 32, and 06). These clinical questions could be considered for updating considering following the ranking of the priority scores (Table 1).
- Eleven clinical questions (11, 12, 33, 08, 37, 16, 36, 34, 05, 35, and 30) have a priority score below 30 and scored lower than five in Item 03 (Context relevance of the clinical question). These clinical questions should not be prioritised for updating. In the case that these clinical questions obtain a similar priority score in the next prioritisation process, it would be considered their inclusion on the static list or their removal. Clinical questions in the static list are not checked as regularly as the other questions included in the clinical guideline [3].
- No relevant differences were observed in number of prioritized clinical questions between the different sections of the CG.

After further discussion with the appraisers, the priority decision of the following clinical questions was modified:

- **Clinical question 01:** This clinical question covers risk factors for glaucoma. Glaucoma is a progressive disease which courses without symptoms until late stages. The identification of people at risk could be beneficial for implementing targeting screening strategies in those who needed. Appraisers considered that the evidence has been evolving in the area, and a review is needed. Clinical question 01 was classified as “Clinical questions prioritised for updating”.
- **Clinical questions 36 and 34:** These questions cover different techniques of anaesthesia in glaucoma surgery. Appraisers considered that there is variability in the clinical practice in this area, and a review could be needed. Clinical questions 36 and 34 were classified as “Clinical questions that could be prioritised for updating”.

TABLE 1. RANKING OF PRIORITY SCORES

Clinical Question	Priority score ^a	Standard deviation ^b	Item score 01 ^{c,d}	Item score 02 ^{c,d}	Item score 03 ^{c,d}	Item score 04 ^{c,d}	Item score 05 ^{c,d}	Item score 06 ^{c,d}
CQ38	31.69	6.13	3.46	4.23	6.00	6.00	6.31	5.69
CQ22	31.31	4.37	3.15	3.62	6.23	6.23	6.31	5.77
CQ14	31.08	4.01	3.46	4.15	6.31	5.54	6.23	5.38
CQ18	30.92	4.46	3.00	5.31	6.08	5.31	5.77	5.46
CQ21	30.77	4.09	3.23	3.08	6.23	6.31	6.38	5.54
CQ31*	30.15	4.56	3.46	6.00	6.00	5.54	6.31	5.46
CQ15	30.00	4.43	2.92	4.46	5.46	5.85	5.77	5.54
CQ03	29.46	4.20	3.08	3.38	5.62	5.77	6.31	5.31
CQ23	29.38	4.03	3.62	3.08	5.85	6.00	6.00	4.85
CQ02	29.08	3.84	2.46	3.31	5.77	5.85	6.15	5.54
CQ17	28.85	5.40	3.00	4.38	5.15	5.69	5.69	4.92
CQ29	28.54	4.35	2.92	3.23	5.69	5.92	5.77	5.00
CQ25	28.38	5.44	3.46	2.85	5.46	6.08	5.92	4.62
CQ24	28.23	3.22	2.69	2.77	6.23	6.00	6.15	4.38
CQ01	27.92	3.82	2.38	2.54	6.00	6.00	6.08	4.92
CQ28	27.54	5.36	2.77	3.77	5.00	5.54	5.15	5.31
CQ04	26.92	5.39	2.46	3.23	5.23	5.46	5.23	5.31
CQ27	26.69	2.46	2.23	2.62	5.15	5.62	5.69	5.38
CQ20	26.62	4.25	3.00	2.23	5.15	5.62	5.38	5.23
CQ19	25.92	6.05	2.46	3.31	4.92	5.46	5.08	4.69
CQ26	24.15	4.54	2.00	2.85	4.77	5.00	4.92	4.62
CQ10	24.15	5.87	1.92	3.46	4.85	5.00	4.77	4.15
CQ07	24.15	6.28	2.54	2.23	4.77	5.31	4.77	4.54
CQ13	23.92	5.47	2.15	2.54	4.85	5.15	5.00	4.23
CQ09	23.31	5.54	2.38	2.38	4.62	5.00	4.92	4.00
CQ32	22.85	7.03	2.62	2.46	4.62	5.08	5.00	3.08
CQ06	22.69	7.62	2.31	2.38	4.23	5.15	4.54	4.08
CQ11	22.62	6.59	2.23	2.31	4.31	4.77	4.62	4.38
CQ12	22.15	6.36	2.15	2.54	4.46	4.77	4.54	3.69
CQ33	22.15	7.07	2.54	2.00	4.15	4.77	5.00	3.69
CQ08	22.00	6.04	2.15	2.31	4.31	4.69	4.31	4.23
CQ37	21.92	7.02	2.00	2.00	4.46	5.00	4.92	3.54
CQ16	21.77	9.83	2.62	3.15	3.92	4.23	4.00	3.85
CQ36	20.62	7.16	2.00	1.92	4.15	4.85	4.23	3.46
CQ34	20.54	5.53	2.00	1.77	3.85	4.69	4.69	3.54
CQ05	20.46	6.42	2.31	2.23	3.85	4.23	4.00	3.85
CQ35	20.46	6.67	2.00	1.77	3.92	4.54	4.54	3.69
CQ30	18.31	8.00	2.00	2.38	3.31	4.46	3.31	2.85

Abbreviation: CQ: Clinical question. ^a Priority scores ordered from higher to lower. ^b Standard deviation ordered from lower to higher. ^c Priority items: Item 01 Impact of out-dated recommendations on safety; Item 02 Availability of new relevant evidence; Item 03 Context relevance of the clinical question; Item 04 Methodological applicability of the clinical question; Item 05 Users' interest; and Item 06 Impact on access to health care. ^d Items with a score of 5 or more are highlighted in red. *CQ31 priority score (calculated by adding the values of each item given by each appraiser and dividing these by the number of appraisers) is less than Items scores (calculated by adding the values of all items given by each appraiser and dividing these by the number of appraisers).

FIGURE 1. RANKING OF PRIORITY SCORES

*CQ31 priority score (calculated by adding the values of each item given by each appraiser and dividing these by the number of appraisers) is less than Items scores (calculated by adding the values of all items given by each appraiser and dividing these by the number of appraisers).

8. REFERENCES

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